

Sub Saharan Africa Pentecostalism

also known as "Spirit Filled Movement, Charismatic Movement"

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Entry tags: African Pentecostalism, Pentacostal, African Religions, Religious Group

European missionaries brought Christianity to Sub Saharan Africa with the goal of converting the population of the region. They were indeed successful in that the local population took Christianity and made it their own. Hence was born African Independent Churches in the early twentieth century leading later to the Pentecostal movement. After the wave of independences from colonial rule in the 1960s, the independent churches thrived until the 1970s when the Pentecostal movement which was at that point an underground movement became full blown. It is now becoming the dominant form of Christianity in Africa attracting converts from all religions, tribal and ethnic groups, and all walks of life. The movement is defined by the day of Pentecost and refers to the encounter with God in the Bible's book of the Acts of the apostles. Pentecostals believe they receive an impartation of God's spirit when they confess the name of Jesus. Its main pillars are the concept of being born again, the baptism of the Holy Spirit, speaking in tongue, the divine healing, the eschatological belief of the return of Jesus Christ, and all wrapped in the concept of the full gospel. First, the concept of 'born again' refers to a spiritual birth of an individual which in the African context connect the person to the invisible world. Second, the baptism of the Holy Spirit is a Christian concept of spiritual empowerment which is also found in African spiritual belief which gives the person a spiritual awareness and discernment. Third, the divine healing mimics African belief that a person can be supernaturally healed in opposition to modern medicine. Finally, the return of Jesus Christ is similar to African eschatological belief that there is an invisible world out there which controls the visible world. In fact, African cosmology assumes two worlds: one which is invisible and populated with spirits and the other which is the visible world. The interaction between the invisible and visible worlds determines human's faith. Pentecostals practice exorcisms where evil spirits are cast out followed with weeping, laughing, and screaming. They engage in what is known as spiritual warfare, praying, and fasting. These beliefs are ingrained in Africans' psyche and were comfortably found in Pentecostal belief generating what is known as African Pentecostalism. It gives people a sense of self, meaning, and reconcile years of exploitation with the newfound identity. It encourages free enterprise, hard work, and self-determination.

Date Range: 1907 CE - 2022 CE

Region: Sub Saharan Africa

Region tags: Africa, Eastern Africa, Western Africa, Southern Africa

This region is the geographic area of Africa that lies below the Saharan Desert.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: African Pentecostalism: An Introduction. 2008. Ogbu Kalu. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Source 2: Pentecostalism and Development: Churches, NGOs and Social Change in Africa. 2012. Edited by Dena Freeman. Jerusalem: Palgrave Macmillan
- Source 3: The End-Time Army: Charismatic Movements in Modern Nigeria. 2006. Matthews A. Ojo. Asmara: Africa World Press, Inc

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1400 CE - 2020 CE

- Source 1: The Go-Between God: The Holy Spirit and the Christian Mission. 1972. John V. Taylor. Eugene: Wipf & Stock
- Source 2: Contemporary Pentecostal Christianity: Interpretations from an African Context. 2013. J. Kwabena Asamoah-Gyadu. Eugene: Wipf & Stock
- Source 3: les pentecotistes du Burkina-Faso: Mariage, Pouvoir et Guerison. 2003. Pierre-Joseph Laurent. Paris Karthala.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1400 CE - 2020 CE

Online sources for understanding this subject:

–Source 1 URL: <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/13617670903371548?journalCode=cjbv20>

–Source 1 Description: African Pentecostalism David J. Garrard. Published online: 15 Dec 2009

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2020 CE

–Source 1 URL: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=7bVUARoSFnQ>

–Source 1 Description: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=tcP9ITthlvs>

–Source 2 URL: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=UFZmgIzi_Dg

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

–Source 1 URL: <https://www.pewforum.org/2006/10/05/overview-pentecostalism-in-africa/>

–Source 1 Description: Pew Research Center is a United States non profit center which is involved in research about issues of interest to the global public.

–Source 2 URL: <https://www.rccg.org/>

–Source 2 Description: The Redeemed Christian Church of God is one of the largest Pentecostal churches in Sub Saharan Africa located in Nigeria

–Source 3 URL: <https://www.cie-mia.org/fr/>

–Source 3 Description: International Evangelism Center - African Interior Mission is one the largest Pentecostal churches in French speaking African countries

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: The Pentecostals are in contact with the rest of the population in the region including people from the other religious groups such as Catholics, other protestant churches, Africa Traditional Religion practitioners. Members come from all segments of each country where the churches are located.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1400 CE - 2020 CE

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

Notes: The Pentecostal movement is extremely competitive in attracting Muslims, Catholics, and other protestants like evangelicals, Lutherans, and Methodists. While the number of its membership is increasing, the numbers of other religions are decreasing.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1400 CE - 2020 CE

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– No

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– No

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– Yes

Notes: In the Sahel region and in northern Nigeria particularly, the contact has led to violence and in some cases to death. For example, the rise of Boko Haram (means Western education is forbidden or is a sin) in the northern Nigerian is related to the rise and activism of Pentecostalism in the region (<https://rlp.hds.harvard.edu/faq/pentecostalism-nigeria>)

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

Notes: Assignment for religious affiliation for the Pentecostals is done through confessing Jesus Christ and accepting Him as Lord and Savior. Members later go through water baptism after/before taking membership class.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1400 CE - 2020 CE

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1400 CE - 2020 CE

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– Yes

Notes: Assignment for religious affiliation for the Pentecostal is done through confessing Jesus Christ and accepting Him as Lord and Savior.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1400 CE - 2020 CE

↳ Assigned by class:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1400 CE - 2020 CE

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– Yes

Notes: Pentecostals generally admit that confessing Jesus Christ as Lord and Savior should be done at an age where the confessing individual is conscious and responsible for his engagement.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1400 CE - 2020 CE

↳ Assigned by gender:

– No

Notes: Both men and women serve at the highest level of Pentecostal churches

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1400 CE - 2020 CE

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– Yes

Notes: After the personal confession accepting Jesus Christ as Lord and Savior, follow the spirit baptism and the water baptism or vice versa.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1400 CE - 2020 CE

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– Yes [specify]: The baptism of the Holy Spirit

Notes: The baptism of the Holy Spirit can intervene at any time before the individual even confesses Jesus Christ as his Savior and Lord.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1400 CE - 2020 CE

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Yes

Notes: Pentecostals actively organize evangelism missions, crusades, tract distributions, and publicly display their intent to convert any person based on the biblical recommendation to bring the good news to the end of the world. https://www.humboldt-foundation.de/pls/web/wt_show.text_page?p_text_id=45680934 (courtesy of Andrew Esiobo from <https://www.humboldt-foundation.de/web/kosmos-humboldtians-in-focus-101-3.html>)

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1400 CE - 2020 CE

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for religious professionals:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1400 CE - 2020 CE

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for all adherents:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1400 CE - 2020 CE

↳ Is missionary work mandated for religious professionals:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1400 CE - 2020 CE

↳ Is missionary work mandated for all adherents:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1400 CE - 2020 CE

↳ Is proselytization coercive:

– No

Notes: Proselytization is not coercive because converts usually join the pentecostal movement voluntarily seeking personal fulfillment. In some cases, converts come to the movement seeking healing, prayer for good jobs and peaceful marital relations.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1400 CE - 2020 CE

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

Notes: Pentecostals are not officially engaged in politics. However due to their growing number they

have a political leverage and use it to promote policies that they deem in their own interest.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1400 CE - 2020 CE

↳ Are the priests paid by polity:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1400 CE - 2020 CE

↳ Is religious infrastructure paid for by the polity:

– No

↳ Are the head of the polity and the head of the religion the same figure:

– No

↳ Are political officials equivalent to religious officials:

– No

↳ Is religious observance enforced by the polity:

– Yes

Notes: Religious observances like Christmas, Ascension, Pentecost Day, Easter etc... are enforced in some of the countries.

↳ Polity legal code is roughly coterminous with religious code:

– No

↳ Polity provides preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax, exemption)

– Yes

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Notes: There is no conception of apostasy in the Pentecostal movement, However, splitting occurs often in the Pentecostal movement due to doctrinal and theological differences which lead to the formation of different churches. The leaving member is often considered as an apostate. the latter leaves his parent church to form his own church.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1400 CE - 2020 CE

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 150000000

Notes: The Pew Forum's analysis of Center for the Study for the Study of Global Christianity (CSGC) data estimates that about eight-in-ten of the world's pentecostals reside either in sub-Saharan Africa (44%).... According to this analysis, 15% of the total population in sub-Saharan Africa is pentecostal (<https://www.pewforum.org/2011/12/19/global-christianity-movements-and-denominations/>).

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Estimated population, percentage of sample region: 15

Notes: the number of Pentecostals is continuing to grow and includes former Muslims, Catholics, African traditional practitioners, and other Protestant churches.

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Large official religious group with smaller religious groups also openly allowed

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: For instance, Enoch Adeboye is known as the General Overseer of the Redeemed Christian Church of God (RCCG). The RCCG has branches in most countries in Sub-Saharan Africa and even in the diaspora all over the world. Visit his website at: <https://eaadeboye.com/>

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

Notes: Depending on the size of the church, there is a lead pastor followed by regional pastors and then local pastors. Each local church has a group of elders who act as the executive officers and the members usually play the role of a general assembly which vote on important issues especially financial issues.

↳ A single leader of a local community:

– Yes

↳ Multiple religious communities each with its own leader, no hierarchy among these leaders:

– No

↳ "Regional" leaders who oversee one or more local leader(s) (e.g. bishops):

– Yes

↳ A single leader for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– No

↳ A council or group of leaders for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– No

↳ Estimate how many levels there are in the hierarchy of religious leadership:

– Number of levels [numeric value]: 2

Notes: There is one lead pastor (General Overseer in the case of the Redeemed Church) and then there are national pastors in each country.

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– Yes

Notes: Through their closeness to the Scripture and the high god, leaders are assumed to develop powers that they can use to heal, prophesy to their members. Leaders use healing power for exorcism, to cure diseases, to bless members. In African conception disease is not only physical condition. It is also spiritual. Similar to the village medicine man, the leader uses his power to find out the mystical cause of the disease, to find out who is responsible or has sent it to the sick person. Then uses his power to heal the person.

↳ Powers are acquired by individual deeds carried out in past lives:

– No

- ↳ Powers are acquired by individual deeds carried out in the current life:
 - Yes
- ↳ Powers are inherited:
 - No
- ↳ Powers are culturally transmitted from a supernatural being:
 - No
- ↳ Powers are culturally transmitted from another human (e.g. teacher):
 - No
- ↳ Powers are associated with leadership office they assume:
 - No
- ↳ Are religious leaders chosen:
 - Yes
 - ↳ A leader chooses his/her own replacement:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Depending on the conception of the local church due to the diversity of in Pentecostal movement.
 - ↳ A leader's retinue or ministers chooses the new leader:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Depending on the conception of the local church due to the diversity in the Pentecostal movement.
 - ↳ Other leaders in the religious group choose that leader:
 - No
 - ↳ A political leader chooses the leader:
 - No
 - ↳ Other members of the leader's congregation choose the leader:
 - Yes
 - ↳ All members of the religious group in the sample region participate in choosing the leader:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Communication with supernatural power(s) believed to be part of the selection process:
 - Yes
- ↳ Are leaders considered fallible:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Charges of fallibility made by a leader's own followers:

– Yes

↳ Charges of fallibility made by other leaders in the religious group:

– No

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a political ruler:

– No

↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:

– Yes

Notes: Due to the diversity in the Pentecostal movement, the religious leaders might or not require the disciples to obediently and unquestionably accept the leaders pronouncements on all matters. In a rare and extreme case in South Africa, a controversial leader ask his church members to eat grass (<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=CxsudMEdg7E>)

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Notes: The Bible is the written text of Pentecostal. the Bible is generally considered as holy, reliable, inerrant, and of divine inspiration.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1400 CE - 2020 CE

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1400 CE - 2020 CE

↳ Are they oral:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1400 CE - 2020 CE

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

Notes: For Pentecostals, the stories contained in the Bible are of divine inspiration. There is an emphasis on chapter two of the book of the Acts of the Apostles when the first Christians were filled with the Holy Spirit spoke in different tongues.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1400 CE - 2020 CE

↳ Revealed by a high god:

– Yes

Notes: The high god is known in Pentecostalism as God the Father.

Specific to this answer:

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↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

– Yes

Notes: The filling of the Holy Spirit is the promise that Jesus made to his disciples before dying on the cross. In John 3:16 he said: But when he, the Spirit of truth, comes, he will guide you into all the truth. He will not speak on his own; he will speak only what he hears, and he will tell you what is yet to come.

Specific to this answer:

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↳ Inspired by high god:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1400 CE - 2020 CE

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

– Yes

Notes: The Holy Spirit is the communicator between the high god and humans.

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– Yes

Notes: For Pentecostals, Jesus Christ is both human and God. He is considered as the manifestation of god in human flesh and known as God the son.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1400 CE - 2020 CE

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1400 CE - 2020 CE

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

– No

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

– No

Notes: Each group member can interpret the Bible through the power of the Holy Spirit. This is usually understood as the Rhema, the revealed word. According to Pentecostals the Holy Spirit can give different meaning of the same verse to different group members.

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– No

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– No

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Notes: Since the 1970s, new church buildings are springing all over the region. The most famous is in the Redemption Camp in Nigeria which is in itself a city (<https://www.theguardian.com/cities/2017/sep/11/eat-pray-live-lagos-nigeria-megachurches-redemption-camp>)

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1400 CE - 2020 CE

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1400 CE - 2020 CE

Is iconography present:

– Yes

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– Only religious public space

Notes: The cross without the image of Jesus is the only accepted iconography.

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):

– No

↳ Portrayals of afterlife:

– No

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):

– Yes

↳ Humans:

– No

↳ Other features of iconography:

– No

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– No

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

Notes: Some the Pentecostal churches require their members to undertake pilgrimages to the Holy Land in Jerusalem and its surroundings. These pilgrimages are organized each year and in some cases members wear a lapel on their chest to show they have already undertaken their pilgrimage.

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:
– Optional (common)

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: There is a distinction between human's soul, body, and spirit, each playing a distinct role in human life.

Specific to this answer:

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↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

Notes: The spirit is the center of the God's renewal thought and the mind is the center of human thought.

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Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: The second coming of Jesus is the Pentecostal eschatological belief which will inaugurate the afterlife. According to Pentecostals, the resurrection of Jesus is a proof of the afterlife.

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↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “above” space:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “below” space:

– No

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:

– No

↳ Afterlife located in "other" space:

– Yes [specify]: Heaven

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1400 CE - 2020 CE

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– No

Notes: The corpse is buried in a grave.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1400 CE - 2020 CE

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1400 CE - 2020 CE

Are grave goods present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1400 CE - 2020 CE

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1400 CE - 2020 CE

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1400 CE - 2020 CE

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1400 CE - 2020 CE

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– No

Notes: However a family which is part of a local church might have a family tomb used for burials.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1400 CE - 2020 CE

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1400 CE - 2020 CE

↳ Other formal burial type:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: Pentecostals believe in Angels, spirits, and demons.

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: The supreme high god in African Pentecostalism is God the Father.

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– Yes

Notes: According to Pentecostals, the God that Jesus Christ calls father is a good god who has forgiven all human sins through grace showing his goodness.

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– No

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Notes: For Pentecostals, their God is all knowing God.

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– Yes [specify]: God created the world in Genesis 1

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: The high god can change a particular situation to benefit a person who obey his word. For instance, African Pentecostal teachings assume bitterness can cause diseases such cancer, ulcer, and heartburn. By freeing oneself from holding grudge against others, the high god can supernaturally heal the believer. In addition, Similar to blood sacrifice in African cosmology, African Pentecostals believe the sacrifice of Jesus and his blood can protect against any spiritual attack.

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

– Yes

Notes: The supreme high god rewards good deeds such as caring for the sick, the poor, and the orphan similar to ancestral belief which puts the community before the individual including the most vulnerable members of the community.

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– No

Notes: African Pentecostals believe the supreme high god is a good god and that Jesus has taken all the punishment that believers deserve on himself in a reference to Isaiah 53:4-5.

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– No

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:

– No

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– No

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: Omnipotence, Omnipresent, Forgiving, compassionate, caring, good, merciful

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– Yes

Notes: Pentecostals believe in prophecy. They believe he communicates with the living through the Holy Spirit.

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– No

Notes: However, in the manifest presence of the supreme high god, evil and impure spirits cannot stand and the believer who is possessed enters in a trance until his deliverance similar to the intervention of the village priest who uses his power to calm the possessed individual.

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– Yes [specify]: Through the Holy Spirit

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: Pentecostals believe in the existence of demonic spirits, angels, and good spirits.

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: Depending on the individual spiritual maturity level.

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Notes: The Holy Spirit is considered as part of the trinity and is fundamental to Pentecostal belief. Pentecostals believe he lives within their spirit and is everywhere they go.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):
 - Yes
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):
 - Yes
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):
 - Yes
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
 - Yes
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:
 - Yes [specify]: The belief is that the Holy Spirit knows a person before he was conceived in his mother's womb.
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings can reward:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings can punish:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:
 - No
- ↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:
 - No
- ↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:
 - Yes
- ↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:
 - No

↳ Organized hierarchically:
– No

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:
– No

↳ Other organization for pantheon:
– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

Notes: Because of the omnipresence of God the Father and the Holy Spirit indwelling in believers' spirits, everything the believer is doing is watched.

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:
Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

Notes: Stemming from Africans' belief in the power of the invisible world to control the visible world, African Pentecostals value the prompting of the Holy Spirit which is based on being honest. Members are taught to believe that grieving the Holy Spirit can lead to major failure in knowing the future.

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Yes

Notes: With the Pentecostal conversion, African Pentecostals reject most of their ancestral taboos and espouse the New Testament biblical taboos.

↳ Food:
– Yes

Notes: It is forbidden to knowingly eat food sacrificed to idols 1 Corinthians 8; 1 Corinthians 10:28.

↳ Sacred space(s):
– No

Notes: With Pentecostals there is no particular sacred space but the believer has to worship in spirit and truth and that can be done anywhere at any time.

↳ Sacred object(s):
– Yes

Notes: The Bible, the holy communion.

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:
– Yes [specify]: The Holy Spirit cares about believers and unbelievers.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:
– Yes

↳ Adultery:
– Yes
Notes: Adultery is considered as a sin.

↳ Incest:
– Yes
Notes: Incest is considered as a sin.

↳ Other sexual practices:
– Yes [specify]: fornication, homosexuality, abortion are believed to be sins.
Notes: In African ancestral belief, fornication, abortion, and especially homosexuality is seen as unnatural sexual practice which is reinforced within the Pentecostal movement. Please read this article about homosexuality and Pentecostalism in Zambia:[http://eprints.whiterose.ac.uk/81954/3/SWC%20Homosexuality%2C%20Politics%20and%20Pentecostal%](http://eprints.whiterose.ac.uk/81954/3/SWC%20Homosexuality%2C%20Politics%20and%20Pentecostal%20)

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Yes [specify]: Drunkenness, jealousy, envy, selfish ambition, hatred, orgies, idolatry, and fits of rage are the acts of flesh described in Galatians 5.

Notes: African Pentecostals espouse these acts of flesh as hindering any spiritual growth.

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Notes: Sin is considered as the agent of supernatural punishment.

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]

– Yes

Notes: Pentecostals understand that a person's evil action can open door to demons' attacks.

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– No

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– No

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– No

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: Caused by the believer's own immoral and unethical thoughts, actions, and speeches.

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:

– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: Hell fire consists in the afterlife punishment.

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

Notes: The lack of material success, bareness, and any failure is understood either as caused by evil deeds, demons or the devil. These are ancestral beliefs that are transferred to the Pentecostal movement.

↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:

– Yes

- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:
 - Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:
 - Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:
 - Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.
 - Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:
 - No
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:
 - No
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:
 - No
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:
 - No
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:
 - Yes
- ↳ Other [specify]
 - No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– Yes

Notes: A believer become righteous through the self sacrifice of Jesus Christ on the cross and he is justified by faith.

↳ Done only by high god:

– Yes

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– No

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

Notes: The believer's righteous living and obedience lead to earthly and heavenly blessings.

- ↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:
 - No
- ↳ Done to enforce group norms:
 - No
- ↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:
 - No
- ↳ Done randomly:
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Supernatural rewards in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure:
 - No
 - ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory pleasure:
 - No
 - ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of eternal happiness:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as a superior life form:
 - No
 - ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in a superior realm:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Other [specify]
 - Yes
 - Notes: Heaven is generally mention as a superior realm.
- ↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:

– Yes

↳ Other [specify]

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Yes

Notes: Jesus Christ is believed to be the Messiah.

↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

– No

↳ Is the messiah's purpose known:

– Yes

↳ Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule:

– No

↳ Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions:

– Yes

↳ Other purpose:

– Yes [specify]: He will set up the Kingdom of God and reign eternally.

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Believers are recommended to let the Holy Spirit lead them in their lives. The new creature born of the spirit supposes a repentance that is a complete turn around from one's previous life to the new life. For instance, if a new believer used to drink before his conversion, the new life bestowed upon him by the spirit will lead him to stop drinking.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: That is where the religious syncretism comes in. Due to ancestral social norms and the existing belief in the supernatural and witchcraft, the Pentecostal theology either conflicts with the ancestral belief or it merges with it.

↳ What is the nature of this distinction:

– Present (but not emphasized)

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the religious group:

– No

Notes: As stated in Jeremy 31:33 "This is the covenant I will make with the people of Israel after that time," declares the Lord. "I will put my law in their minds and write it on their hearts. I will be their God, and they will be my people. 34 No longer will they teach their neighbor, or say to one another, 'Know the Lord,' because they will all know me, from the least of them to the greatest," declares the Lord. "For I will forgive their wickedness and will remember their sins no more."

↳ Moral norms apply to:

– Only specialized religious class

Notes: These moral norms only apply to Pentecostal believers who have confessed Jesus Christ as their lord and savior.

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:

– Yes

Notes: Luke 6:31 31 Do to others as you would have them do to you.

↳ Courage (in battle):

– No

Notes: 5. Matthew 5:38-48 "You have heard that it was said, 'Eye for eye, and tooth for tooth. But I tell you, do not resist an evil person. If anyone slaps you on the right cheek, turn to them the other cheek also. And if anyone wants to sue you and take your shirt, hand over your coat as well. If anyone forces you to go one mile, go with them two miles. Give to the one who asks you, and do not turn away from the one who wants to borrow from you. "You have heard that it was said, 'Love your neighbor and hate your enemy.' But I tell you, love your enemies and pray for those who persecute you, that you may be children of your Father in heaven. He causes his sun to rise on the evil and the good, and sends rain on the righteous and the unrighteous. If

you love those who love you, what reward will you get? Are not even the tax collectors doing that? And if you greet only your own people, what are you doing more than others? Do not even pagans do that? Be perfect, therefore, as your heavenly Father is perfect."

↳ **Courage (generic):**

– Yes

Notes: 1 Corinthians 16:13 Be on your guard; stand firm in the faith; be men of courage; be strong.

↳ **Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:**

– Yes

Notes: Matthew 9:35-38, Jesus went through all the towns and villages, teaching in their synagogues, proclaiming the good news of the kingdom and healing every disease and sickness. When he saw the crowds, he had compassion on them, because they were harassed and helpless, like sheep without a shepherd. Then he said to his disciples, "The harvest is plentiful but the workers are few. Ask the Lord of the harvest, therefore, to send out workers into his harvest field."

↳ **Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:**

– Yes

Notes: Colossians 3:13 – Bearing with one another and, if one has a complaint against another, forgiving each other; as the Lord has forgiven you, so you also must forgive.

↳ **Generosity / charity:**

– Yes

Notes: 2 Corinthians 9:6-8 Remember this: Whoever sows sparingly will also reap sparingly, and whoever sows generously will also reap generously. Each of you should give what you have decided in your heart to give, not reluctantly or under compulsion, for God loves a cheerful giver. And God is able to bless you abundantly, so that in all things at all times, having all that you need, you will abound in every good work.

↳ **Selflessness / selfless giving:**

– Yes

Notes: Luke 6:35 - But love your enemies, and do good, and lend, expecting nothing in return, and your reward will be great, and you will be sons of the Most High, for he is kind to the ungrateful and the evil.

↳ **Righteousness / moral rectitude:**

– Yes

Notes: Romans 1:17 - For in it the righteousness of God is revealed from faith to faith; as it is written, "But the righteous man shall live by faith."

↳ **Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:**

– Yes

Notes: Mark 7:20 - "What comes out of a person is what defiles them.

↳ **Respectfulness / courtesy:**

– Yes

Notes: Romans 12:10 - Be devoted to one another in love. Honor one another above yourselves.

↳ **Familial obedience / filial piety:**

– Yes

Notes: Ephesians 5:21-32 Submitting yourselves one to another in the fear of God. Wives, submit yourselves unto your own husbands, as unto the Lord. For the husband is the head of

the wife, even as Christ is the head of the church: and he is the saviour of the body. Therefore as the church is subject unto Christ, so let the wives be to their own husbands in every thing. Husbands, love your wives, even as Christ also loved the church, and gave himself for it; That he might sanctify and cleanse it with the washing of water by the word, That he might present it to himself a glorious church, not having spot, or wrinkle, or any such thing; but that it should be holy and without blemish. So ought men to love their wives as their own bodies. He that loveth his wife loveth himself. For no man ever yet hated his own flesh; but nourisheth and cherisheth it, even as the Lord the church: For we are members of his body, of his flesh, and of his bones. For this cause shall a man leave his father and mother, and shall be joined unto his wife, and they two shall be one flesh. This is a great mystery: but I speak concerning Christ and the church. Ephesians 6: 1-4 - Children, obey your parents in the Lord: for this is right. Honour thy father and mother; which is the first commandment with promise; That it may be well with thee, and thou mayest live long on the earth. And, ye fathers, provoke not your children to wrath: but bring them up in the nurture and admonition of the Lord.

↳ Fidelity /loyalty:

– Yes

Notes: Luke 19:17 - And he said to him, 'Well done, good slave, because you have been faithful in a very little thing, you are to be in authority over ten cities.'

↳ Cooperation:

– Yes

Notes: Romans 15:5-6 - Now may the God who gives perseverance and encouragement grant you to be of the same mind with one another according to Christ Jesus, so that with one accord you may with one voice glorify the God and Father of our Lord Jesus Christ.

↳ Independence /creativity /freedom:

– Yes

Notes: 2 Corinthians 3:17 - Now the Lord is the Spirit, and where the Spirit of the Lord is, there is liberty.

↳ Moderation /frugality:

– Yes

Notes: Colossians 4:6 - Let your speech always be with grace, as though seasoned with salt, so that you will know how you should respond to each person.

↳ Forbearance /fortitude /patience:

– Yes

Notes: Colossians 3:13 - bearing with one another, and forgiving each other, whoever has a complaint against anyone; just as the Lord forgave you, so also should you.

↳ Diligence /self-discipline /excellence:

– Yes

Notes: Hebrew 6:11 - We want each of you to show this same diligence to the very end, so that what you hope for may be fully realized.

↳ Assertiveness /decisiveness /confidence /initiative:

– Yes

Notes: 2 Corinthians 3:12 - Therefore having such a hope, we use great boldness in our speech.

↳ Strength (physical):

– Yes

Notes: 2 Corinthians 12:10 - That is why, for Christ's sake, I delight in weaknesses, in insults, in hardships, in persecutions, in difficulties. For when I am weak, then I am strong.

↳ Power / status / nobility:

– Yes

Notes: Colossians 1:11 - being strengthened with all power according to his glorious might so that you may have great endurance and patience,

↳ Humility / modesty:

– Yes

Notes: Ephesians 4:2 Be completely humble and gentle; be patient, bearing with one another in love.

↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:

– Yes

Notes: Hebrews 13:5 - Keep your lives free from the love of money and be content with what you have, because God has said, "Never will I leave you; never will I forsake you.

↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:

– Yes

Notes: James 1:2-3 2 Consider it pure joy, my brothers and sisters, whenever you face trials of many kinds, because you know that the testing of your faith produces perseverance.

↳ Optimism / hope:

– Yes

Notes: 2 Corinthians 3:4-5 - Such confidence we have through Christ toward God. Not that we are adequate in ourselves to consider anything as coming from ourselves, but our adequacy is from God.

↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:

– Yes

Notes: Colossians 3:15 - Let the peace of Christ rule in your hearts, since as members of one body you were called to peace. And be thankful.

↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:

– Yes

Notes: Hebrews 12:28 - Therefore, since we receive a kingdom which cannot be shaken, let us show gratitude, by which we may offer to God an acceptable service with reverence and awe.

↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:

– Yes

Notes: Romans 10:17 - So faith comes from hearing, and hearing through the word of Christ.

↳ Wisdom / understanding:

– Yes

Notes: 1 Corinthians 1:25 - For the foolishness of God is wiser than human wisdom, and the weakness of God is stronger than human strength.

↳ Discernment / intelligence:

– Yes

Notes: 1 John 4:1 - Beloved, do not believe every spirit, but test the spirits to see whether they are from God, for many false prophets have gone out into the world.

↳ Beauty / attractiveness:

– Yes

Notes: 1 Peter 3:3-4 - Your beauty should not come from outward adornment, such as elaborate hairstyles and the wearing of gold jewelry or fine clothes. Rather, it should be that of your inner self, the unfading beauty of a gentle and quiet spirit, which is of great worth in God's sight.

↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:

– Yes

Notes: 1 John 1:9 - If we confess our sins, he is faithful and just and will forgive us our sins and purify us from all unrighteousness.

↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes [specify]: compassion, caring about others, meekness, gentleness, self control, love peace, joy

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: It does not require sexual abstinence but believers are recommended to let the Holy Spirit lead them in their sexual life. Most Pentecostals stated after their conversion they were not forced to stop having multiple partners but the power of the Holy Spirit led them to stick to one partner or to sexual abstinence for bachelors.

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Yes

Notes: Occasional fasting is required to be close to God. Depending on the situation, Pentecostals fast when they want to request something (job, marriage for instance) from God. Isaiah 58 and Matthew 6: 16-18 describe when, why, and how a believer should fast.

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Notes: However, it is forbidden to eat food and animals sacrificed to idols (1 Corinthians 8)

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her

actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Notes: However voluntary offerings and payment of tithes are recommended.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Notes: honesty, piety, chastity are recommended and members are recommended to let the Holy Spirit lead them.

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– No

Notes: Water baptism, family devotions

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale "ceremonies" and "festivals."

– Yes

Notes: Most members participate in festivals, crusades, meetings, sharing the communion, and church services.

↳ On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Number of participants: 100

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Average interval [hours]: 1

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized

way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– Yes

Notes: The Bible is the reference in any Pentecostal rituals.

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– Yes

Notes: Again the bible is the reference in ritual performances.

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– Yes

Notes: The sharing of communion is synchronic.

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: Most of the members are converts from other religions

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Yes

Notes: Some of the Pentecostal churches are so well organized in some of the states that they provide needed public services that should have been provided by the states.

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: The states provide some of the needed services.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Yes

Notes: Most of the Pentecostal churches provide vocational training and social services to the most needy in the society.

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Yes

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Most of the Pentecostal churches have institutions which care about the elderly and infirm.

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

Notes: Some of the Pentecostal churches provide K-12, and higher education to their members and the rest of the population.

↳ Is formal education restricted to religious professionals:

– No

↳ Is such education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: there are state sponsored institutions open to all the population including the Pentecostals.

↳ Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Notes: Each Pentecostal church organized itself in different ministries which operates as a bureaucracy to cater to the need of their members.

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: Group adherents interact with the state bureaucracy.

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– Yes

Notes: Depending on the state, some of the Pentecostal churches are involved in water management on their own properties.

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The states are the main water management institutions.

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– Yes

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The states are the main providers of transportation infrastructure.

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Yes

Notes: Members are encouraged to tithe.

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: taxes are levied by the states in which the churches are located.

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– Yes

Notes: Some of the largest groups provide their own security.

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– No

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– Yes

Notes: Most religious organizations are required to register within their states.

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Because group's adherent are citizens of given countries, they are subject to their states' legal codes.

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Notes: African Pentecostals use the Gregorian calendar.

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

↳ Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards
- Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

↳ Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Fishing
- Pastoralism
- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards
- Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

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